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Impact of Perceived Instructor (University Teachers) Credibility on Academic Dishonesty and Classroom Incivility Among University Students

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Abstract

Classroom incivility and academic dishonesty are among the most pressing issues in the educational system at present that are growing continuously. To deal with these issues, it's necessary to highlight the predictors of these behaviors. The main objective of this study was to fill this gap by studying the impact of perceived instructor credibility on academic dishonesty and classroom incivility among Pakistani students on the basis of General Model of Instructional Communication (GMIC). The sample selected for this research consisted of 300 BS students from different universities of Pakistan. Data was collected by using the Source Credibility Scale (competence, goodwill, trust subscales), Child and Youth Classroom Incivility Scale and Academic Dishonesty Scale. Different types of statistical analysis were performed using SPSS. The results of the study indicated negative relationship of perceived instructor credibility with academic dishonesty and classroom incivility. The results concluded that perceived instructor credibility dimensions such as competence and trustworthiness are significant predictor of academic dishonesty and classroom incivility whereas goodwill is not a significant predictor of academic dishonesty and classroom incivility. Beside this, the study concluded that students who are involved in classroom incivility have greater chances to be involved in academic dishonesty and vice versa. Moreover, male students and low achievers are more likely to involve in these behaviours. These behaviors in the education system can be overcome by increasing instructors/university teachers' credibility. Beside this, more focus on male

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students, low achievers and students involving in lower level of classroom incivility can prevent these behaviours to escalate. These steps can be helpful in improving the teaching-learning process and to uplift the standard of education.

Keywords. Perceived Instructor/university teacher credibility, Competence, Goodwill, Trustworthiness, Academic dishonesty, Classroom incivility.

Introduction

Classroom incivility is a growing problem that hinders learning in academic settings around the world. It was once thought of as simply unpleasant classroom practices (Nilson & Jackson, 2004). The definition of classroom incivility has changed from generation to generation (Brubacher & Rudy, 1997; Cohon, 1998). Behind this ambiguity, the reason is that defining classroom incivility is a subjective phenomenon. One person may consider a behavior uncivil and another may not (Bjorklund & Rehling, 2009).

Incivility as a whole is defined as -any low intensity, deviant behavior with involves ambiguous intent to cause harm (Andersson & Pearson, 1999). When it comes specifically to classroom incivility, it can be defined as those behaviors that interfere with a cooperative learning environment (Feldmann, 2001) .Such actions and behaviors in the classroom may involve student conversation during lectures, books packing before completing the lesson and making fun of other classmates who responded wrong but classroom incivility is not limited to only these behaviors.

According to Feldmann (2001), incivility in the classroom negatively impacts the learning environment by interfering with the teacher's instruction. Nonetheless, there are two possible reasons why educators can choose not to address this issue or even disregard it. Firstly, since classroom incivility is supposed to be low-intensity antisocial conduct, it might be assumed to have no harm and that it will end on its own. Secondly, often interrupting classto address minor uncivil behaviors may cut into the time allotted for teaching the course material. Such behavior in the school setting may likely worsen if teachers choose not to deal with these behaviors (Feldmann, 2001). Additionally, when incivility in the classroom is tolerated, there is a risk that it will develop into more severe antisocial behaviors or lead to detrimental psychosocial effects (Felblinger, 2009; Miller et al., 2014; Spadafora et al., 2020; Volk et al., 2016).

Literature has highlighted civility decline in every field (Jacoby, 1999; Lunday, 2007). The incidence and intensity of classroom incivility in higher education settings have both increased over the past couple of decades, according to several significant researches (Baker et al., 2008; Boice, 1996; Clark, 2008). In Higher education institutes, the primary focus is on the civility decline in the classroom (Alexander-Snow, 2004; Feldmann, 2001). Since such acts can disrupt learning in the classroom, erode students' respect and commitment to the institutions, harm the learning environment, discussions concerning classroom incivility frequently center on the need to reduce student incivility (Feldmann, 2001; Hirschy & Braxton, 2004; Morrissette, 2001).

Besides this, it can be observed from different past studies that one type of disruptive behavior can lead to other forms of disruptive behavior. In 1999, Anderson and Pearson proposed a model related to incivility that was based on workplace organizations. According to this model, the less severe acts of incivility might become

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the first step in a cycle of increasing physical and/or violent behavior, such as harassment, sabotage, vandalism and physical assault. This model is applicable and appropriate for higher education settings, including classroom settings where minor levels of student disruptive behaviors can escalate into more major behavioral incidents. So one of the present focuses of the study is to find out whether students involved in classroom incivility are more prone to be involved in academic dishonesty or not.

Dishonesty is one of the most common phenomena, and it refers to any action performed without honesty. This term refers to a lack of ethics or integrity, lying, cheating or intentionally deceptive behavior. The core component of a large number of rule violations is dishonesty relating to achievement (Munir et al., 2011). Specifically, academic dishonesty can be defined as immoral behavior in an educational setting (Muhammad et al., 2020). This is an inappropriate type of behavior in which students try to gain an unfair advantage in studies for themselves or their friends within the academic community (Grira & Jaeck, 2019). Academic dishonesty resists the development process of different positive values i.e. fairness, honesty etc. It also impacts proper growth in learning and is related to other negative behaviors even in other fields besides education (Krou et al., 2021; Yu et al., 2018) , i.e. in the work environment (Barbaranelli et al., 2018; Bashir & Bala, 2018). Many studies which were conducted on assessing the prevalence of AD, found considerably worrisome amounts of AD in different fields. According to research, this type of behavior is a well-established phenomenon that has become more common in recent times (e.g., Birks et al., 2020; Grira & Jaeck, 2019; Harper et al., 2021), and it is a cross-cultural, multifaceted phenomenon that occurs around the world (Barbaranelli et al., 2018; Bashir & Bala, 2018).

To reduce classroom incivility and academic dishonesty, the identification of factors that lead to these disruptive behaviors is very necessary. Although there are many studies on academic dishonesty and classroom incivility, one of the most important topics in this area that still needs further investigation is -What are the predictors of Academic dishonesty and classroom incivility?

One variable that needs more attention in the literature related to academic dishonesty and classroom incivility is -perceived instructor/teacher credibility. According to Thweatt & McCroskey (1998), Instructor/Teacher credibility refers to the perception of students regarding teachers' competence, trustworthiness, and caring. Credibility is the cornerstone of effective influence since the source credibility determines whether a given influence technique is successful or unsuccessful in the end (Hackman & Johnson, 2013) A source's credibility is seen by recipients in an evaluative way. Most professors want to create favorable student attitudes towards themselves and their subject matter in addition to having students evaluate their instruction favorably. To fulfill their educational goals, instructors must communicate with their students effectively and foster a favorable learning environment. One of the primary factors affecting communication is how a teacher is viewed by his students, or in simple words his image. Credibility as a source is one aspect that contributes to an instructor's overall image.

Literature has identified the impact of instructor credibility on learning outcomes but little research has been done on disruptive behaviors such as classroom incivility and academic dishonesty. It is evident from the literature that students who recognize that

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their teachers are more credible have less probability of engaging in cheating (Anderman et al., 2009). So, it may be possible that students' perception of greater teacher credibility may lead to a decrease in other types of academic dishonesty beside cheating that has never been investigated before. Beside this, most of the research on the impact of perceived instructor credibility on classroom incivility has been performed in Western countries. The present study was an effort to explore the relationship between perceived instructor credibility, academic dishonesty and classroom incivility in the Pakistani population.

Additionally, academic dishonesty is influenced by a number of factors, including individual differences (McCabe & Trevino, 1997). Individual differences include achievement level, parental education, gender, age etc. According to the findings of a study, there is a connection between gender and academic dishonesty (Hasanah, 2016). Moreover, previous researches has also illustrated the role of achievement level in academic dishonesty (Baird Jr, 1980; Bowers, 1964; Hetherington & Feldman, 1964). Besides this, different demographic traits including gender such as being female and desire to pursue advanced studies is associated with reduced incivility (Nordstrom et al., 2009). Although, literature had identified a significant impact of disruptive classroom behaviours on achievement level, (Borg, 2015), there is further need to investigate the relationship between academic achievement level and classroom incivility. Based on above explanation, the present research study also attempted to examine the differences in academic dishonesty and classroom incivility on the basis of gender and student achievement level among Pakistani students.

Theoretical Framework

General Model of Instructional Communication (GMIC)

The main aim of the present research study was to examine the role of perceived instructor credibility on academic dishonesty and classroom incivility. This has been done by using McCroskey et al. (2004), General Model of Instructional Communication (GMIC). According to this model, there are six essential components of instructional communication which are environmental factors, instructor behaviors, instructor traits, student perceptions regarding the instructor, student own traits and student outcomes. All these components can cause significant variation into the instructional communication process. Previous studies have used different components of this model. This study makes use of three of these components i.e. student perceptions of instructor (university teachers) credibility, student individual differences (i.e. gender, students achievement level) as student traits, and student outcomes (in this case academic dishonesty and classroom uncivil behaviors).

Models of Incivility

Incivility is frequently considered a vast concept. Multiple conceptualizations related to the subtypes of incivility are present in the literature. These conceptualizations help in understanding how incivility works and the outcomes of incivility. Firstly, as stated by Marini (2009), there are two distinct continuums along which incivility can be explained: the form, which ranges from indirect to direct behavior, and the function, which ranges from proactive to reactive behavior. Other researchers have concentrated on conceptualizing classroom incivility according to how intense the action is. In general, classroom incivility used to be measured on a

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continuum that ranges from somewhat annoying behavior to more intensive intentionally performed classroom behaviors (Farrell et al., 2016; Feldmann, 2001; Marini, 2009).

Another very important factor that is used to conceptualize classroom incivility is intentionality. According to the two-factor model of classroom incivility, classroom uncivil behaviors may be intentional or unintentional. This two-factor model of classroom incivility has been adopted in the present study.

Factors of Perceived Instructor Credibility

McCroskey & Teven (1999) assert that competence, expertise, Trustworthiness, character and goodwill care are the three components that make up an instructor's credibility.

Competence

Instructor competence (expertness) refers to the extent to which the instructor is perceived as trustworthy and expert in terms of the knowledge/information he shares during the course/lecture (N. P. Freeman, 2011).

Goodwill/care

The second component of perceived instructor credibility is goodwill or caring (McCroskey & Richmond, 2000; McCroskey & Teven, 1999, cited in Myers, 2001). Goodwill refers to the caring behaviour of instructor toward his students or how much the instructor cares about his students wellbeing (McCroskey, 1992, cited in Myers 2001).

Trustworthiness/character

The third component of instructor's credibility is instructor's trustworthiness or instructors character, which is the extent to which the instructor is perceived as trustworthy, nice (Frymier & Thompson 1992, cited in Chory 2007), faithful, honest (M. Freeman, 2011), responsible and kind (McCroskey, 1992).

Factors of Academic Dishonesty

According to Bashir & Bala (2018), academic dishonesty has 6 components/factors such as cheating behaviour, manipulation, taking outside help, plagiarism, falsification and cheating in exams. Based on these components, they developed and validated a scale named as academic dishonesty scale.

Literature Review

The research literature has identified a wide range of behaviors as academic dishonest behavior in the traditional physical learning environment such as helping friends and peers during exams, allowing work to be copied, using prohibited material in papers, obtaining information from friends who have previously taken the exam, taking the exam for someone else, plagiarism, repeated submission of an assignment, presenting other people's work as ones own, or purchasing assignments, collaborating on writing projects with friends when not allowed and adding references to the bibliography without using (Denisova-Schmidt, 2020; Von Dran et al., 2001). In a recently

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published meta-analysis of numerous research studies looking at behaviors in different fields, Krou et al. (2021) divided Academic dishonesty-related behaviors into two categories such as plagiarism and cheating behavior.

Beside this, Bashir & Bala (2018) presented a multidimensional scale for academic dishonesty which classified academic dishonesty into 6 factors such as plagiarism, cheating behavior, falsification, taking outside help, manipulation and cheating in exams. This research study has utilized this classification of academic dishonesty.

Academic dishonesty has long been a problem, but it has recently extended more widely. One of the causes of this rise in academic dishonesty is the expansion of online education and the newly emerging technologies that support these actions (Etgar et al., 2019; Peytcheva-Forsyth et al., 2018; Sarwar et al., 2018). Moreover, literature has identified different causes of academic dishonesty among students that are driven either by intrinsic or extrinsic factors. (Amigud & Lancaster, 2019; Bretag et al., 2019; Kiekkas et al., 2020; Murdock & Anderman, 2006). Literature has also highlighted the influence of different factors including individual differences on academic dishonesty (McCabe & Trevino, 1997). Different researches at different times indicated multiple impact of gender on academic dishonesty. Male students exhibit higher levels of academic dishonesty than female students, according to most of the earlier researches (Antion & Michael, 1983; Haines et al., 1986; Lipson & McGavern, 1993). According to McCabe & Trevino (1997), gender role socialisation theory—which holds that women are more likely than males to be socialised to obey rules—explains the connection between gender and academic dishonesty. According to the results of their study, women were far less likely to cheat.

Additionally, it has been discovered that students with lower academic achievement cheat more frequently than those with greater academic achievement (Baird Jr, 1980; Bowers, 1964; Hetherington & Feldman, 1964). One potential explanation for this difference is that students with lower academic achievement are more inclined to cheat since they stand to benefit more from it and lose less (Leming, 1980). Still, additional research needs to be done to determine how the gender and academic achievement level impacts academic dishonesty.

Academic dishonesty is a type of deviant behaviour (Blankenship & Whitley, 2000). According to previous research, a person engaged in one type of deviant behavior is more likely to engage in additional deviant behaviors as well. Researchers who studied the profile of academic offenders among undergraduate students discovered a high correlation between academic dishonesty and various personal perceptions, academic achievement, and engagement in other risky behaviors (Korn & Davidovitch, 2016).

Besides academic dishonesty, classroom incivility is another type of behavior that affects the classroom environment. Literature has indicated different predictors of uncivil behavior within the class. According to previous research, numerous student personality traits have been linked to incivility such as academic entitlement (Kopp & Finney, 2013), narcissistic tendencies, and consumerism orientation towards academic pursuits (Nordstrom et al., 2009). Additionally, it has been discovered that students become more prone to engage in uncivil behaviors when they experience feelings of powerlessness, anger and helplessness towards the teacher (Clark, 2008). Besides this among demographic traits, being female and wanting to study in graduate school are student demographic characteristics linked to less incivility (Nordstrom et al., 2009).

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Different previous studies have highlighted the relationship between different instructors' behaviors and classroom incivility. A study conducted by (Miller et al., 2014) illustrated the role of instructors' self-disclosure and non-verbal immediacy in creating student classroom incivility. Another very important study investigated the collective effect of different instructor communication variables (i.e. self-disclosure and nonverbal immediacy), different student personality traits and instructor credibility on college classroom incivility. Results indicated that instructor credibility serves the mediating role between instructors'/teachers' behaviors and classroom incivility. Besides this specific student traits are also responsible for classroom incivility (Klebig et al., 2016). Moreover, Chory & Offstein (2017) found that students' perceptions of professors' inappropriate out-of- class behavior lead to students' perception of instructors' lower ethical character which leads to classroom uncivil behaviors.

Instructor/Source credibility has been researched in a variety of situations, including media message production, organizational contexts, and student-teacher interaction (H. R. Freeman, 1988; Hubbell & Chory-Assad, 2005; Priester & Petty, 2003, cited in Dunleavy et al., 2010). As one of the primary sources of information for students in universities, instructors must persuade them of the truth of the information they provide; in other words, they must be credible if students are to learn effectively (Beatty & Behnke, 1980; Teven, 2007). Hence, it is extremely significant for instructors/teachers to be perceived as credible for effective learning and communication. Similarly, research in educational psychology suggests that student relationships with teachers are related to valued outcomes, even though the study of teacher credibility has its roots in the discipline of communications (Noddings, 1992; Pianta & Steinberg, 1992).

A significant sample consisting of middle school students and instructors was studied by Murdock et al. (2001) to determine the association between student-teacher relationships and cheating. The results indicated that academic cheating has less chance to occur when students perceive that their teachers are committed to their work (job) and are respectable for the students. Beside this, Students are less likely to report cheating when they believe their health teachers to be reliable (Anderman et al., 2009). So the main purpose of conducting this study is to find out whether the perception of students regarding their teacher's credibility which is referred to as perceived instructor credibility affects the intensity of classroom incivility and academic dishonesty among the Pakistani population.

Objectives

1. To explore the impact of perceived instructor credibility on academic dishonesty and classroom incivility.
2. To explore differences between high academic achievers and low academic achievers on perceived instructor credibility, classroom incivility, and academic dishonesty.
3. To find out perceived instructor credibility, classroom incivility, and academic dishonesty on the basis of gender.
4. To explore whether students who score high in academic dishonesty also score high in classroom incivility.
5. To explore whether perceived instructor credibility (competence, goodwill,

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trustworthiness) is a predictor of academic dishonesty and classroom incivility

Hypothesis

H1: There will be a negative relationship of perceived instructor credibility with academic dishonesty and classroom incivility.

H2: Students with higher academic grades will be lower on classroom incivility and academic dishonesty as compared to low achievers.

H3: Male students are more likely to be involved in academic dishonesty and classroom incivility as compared to female students.

H4: Academic dishonesty will have a positive relationship with classroom incivility.

H5: Perceived instructor credibility (competence, goodwill, trustworthiness) will negatively predict academic dishonesty and classroom incivility among university students.

Research Method

Research Design

It was a cross-sectional study that explored the correlation between variables i.e. perceived instructor/university teacher credibility, academic dishonesty and classroom incivility where the unit of analysis was university students.

Sample/Participants

The sampling technique used for this research study was convenience sampling. The sample consisted of 300 BS students from different universities of Pakistan which were enrolled in different subjects. About 136 male and 164 female students of the age range 18-25 years participated in this study. The students belong to all social classes such as upper, middle and lower.

Instruments

Demographic sheet

Demographic information such as age, gender, educational level, educational grades/GPA etc was collected with the help of a demographic sheet.

Source Credibility Scale

Teacher credibility was measured by using McCroskey & Teven, (1999) source credibility scale which consisted of 18-item. It's a bipolar scale having three sub-scales such as competence, goodwill and trustworthiness each having 6 items. The scale doesn't have an overall total score and each dimension is scored separately. The alpha reliability of the competence sub-scale is .62, the goodwill sub-scale is .60, and for trustworthiness sub-scale is .57.

Child and Youth Classroom Incivility Scale (CYCIS)

This scale was developed by Spadafora & Volk (2021). This is an eleven-item scale having 2 dimensions such as intentional and unintentional incivility. The scale has a Likert type scoring from 1 indicating never to 5 indicating always. The scale has significant reliability such as $\alpha = .84$ in the present study.

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Academic Dishonesty Scale

Academic dishonesty was assessed by using the academic dishonesty scale which was developed by Ranjan Bala and Hilal Bashir in 2018. It has 23 items related to 6 dimensions of academic dishonesty such as cheating in examination, plagiarism, prior cheating, outside help, falsification and lying about academic assignments. The academic dishonesty scale (ADS) had an adequate reliability of .88 in the current study.

Procedure

First of all, different universities were selected by using convenience sampling. Then a sample of almost 300 BS students was selected. The student's consent was obtained regarding the research. Then the questionnaires consisting of a demographic sheet and other 3 scales such as (Source Credibility Scale, Academic Dishonesty Scale and Child and youth classroom incivility scale) were distributed among the students. After collecting data, it was transferred to SPSS and different statistical analyses such as descriptive statistics, regression, correlation, t-test were run on the data. The results were properly analysed, interpreted and has been explained in the discussion section.

Results

Table 1: Frequencies and percentages of demographic variables of Study (N = 300)

Variables	Category	<i>F</i>	%
Gender	Male	136	45.3%
	Female	164	54.7%
Socio-economic status	Low	59	19.7%
	Middle	174	58%
	Upper	67	22.3%
GPA	2-2.5	26	8.7%
	2.6-3.0	80	26.7%
	3.1-3.5	102	34%
	3.6-4.0	92	30.7%
Degree Program/Dept	Social Sciences	70	23.3%
	Management Sciences	34	11.3%
	Biological sciences	37	12.3%

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Computer Sciences/ IT	24	8.0%
Basic & Applied Sciences	56	18.7%
Engineering	19	6.3%
Other	60	20%

Table 1 presents the demographic information of a sample of 300 BS students. The results indicate that more female students (55%) participated in the study as compared to male students (45%). The data was collected from students of all socioeconomic status with a greater percentage of students from middle-class families (58%). The students were selected randomly from different subjects/fields as indicated in the table with a greater percentage of social science students (23%). Additionally, the student's GPA was also considered with the greatest percentage of students lying within the range of 3.1-3.5GPA.

Table 2: Psychometric Properties of the Study Major Variables/Scales (N=300)

Variables	K	A	M (SD)	Range		Skewness	Kurtosis
				Potential	Actual		
CIn	11	.84	24.89(10.18)	11-55	11-49	.77	-.459
ADS	23	.88	46.31(18.57)	23-115	23-99	.92	-.080
CO	6	.62	27.12(7.12)	6-42	11-41	.28	-.34
GO	6	.60	23.92(8.07)	6-42	10-41	.70	-.47
TR	6	.57	26.37(6.47)	6-42	12-41	.12	-.41

Note. CIn = Child and Youth Classroom Incivility Scale, ADS = Academic Dishonesty Scale; Source Credibility Scale Dimensions(CO=Competence, GO=Goodwill, TR=Trustworthiness Table 2 shows the psychometric properties of the scales used in the study. The

Cronbach alpha value for the Academic Dishonesty Scale was .88(>.70) and for Child and Youth Classroom Incivility Scale was .84(>.70) which indicates a higher internal consistency of the scales. The Cronebeck alpha values of different dimensions of the source credibility scale i.e. Competence, goodwill, and trust are .62, .60, .57, respectively which indicates adequate reliability of the scale.

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Table 3: Mean, Standard Deviations, and t-value for classroom incivility, academic dishonesty and perceived instructor credibility (competence, goodwill, trust) across gender

Variables	Male	Female	t	p	95% CI		Cohen's d
	(n = 136)	(n = 164)			LL	UL	
	M (SD)	M (SD)					
Cin	25.69(10.29)	24.23(10.07)	1.23	.217	-.86	3.78	0.1
AD	49.55(18.74)	43.62(18.05)	2.78	.006	1.74	10.12	0.3
CO	29.60(7.75)	25.06(5.81)	5.78	.000	2.99	6.07	0.6
GO	26.64(8.77)	21.66(6.66)	5.58	.000	3.22	6.73	0.6
TR	27.24(7.20)	25.65(5.71)	2.13	.033	.128	3.06	0.2

Note. AD=Academic dishonesty scale; Dimensions of Source Scale (CO=Competence, GO=Goodwill, TR=Trust); Cin=Classroom Incivility; CI = Confidence Interval; LL = Lower Limit; UL = Upper Limit

The table revealed significant mean differences on the academic dishonesty scale with $t(298)=2.78, p<.01$. Findings showed that boys exhibited higher scores on academic dishonesty ($M=49.55, SD=18.74$) as compared to girls scores ($M=43.62, SD=18.05$). The value of Cohen's d for the academic dishonesty was $0.3(<.50)$ which indicates a very small effect size. Beside this, findings revealed significant mean differences on all dimensions of the source credibility scale (i.e. competence, goodwill, trustworthiness) with higher scores exhibited by boys. The value of Cohen's d for competence and goodwill scales was $0.6(>.50)$ which indicates a moderate effect size and for trust was $0.2(<0.5)$ which indicates a very small effect size. Findings indicated a non-significant mean difference on the classroom incivility scale.

Table 4: Mean, Standard Deviations, and F-value for classroom incivility, academic dishonesty and perceived instructor credibility (competence, goodwill, trust) across achievement levels (determined from GPA categories) (N=300)

Variables	M (SD)	M (SD)	M (SD)	M(SD)	1<2<3			
Cin	23.00(8.59)	27.93(12.14)	25.21(9.73)	22.45(8.47)	4.62	.004	.04	2>3>1>4
AD	44.46(16.60)	54.29(22.86)	46.21(17.01)	40(13.62)	9.26	.000	.08	2>3>1>4

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CO	28.92(7.30)	26.11(8.02)	27.25(7.28)	27.34(5.93)	1.13	.337	.01	1>4>3>2
GO	28.04(7.68)	23.19(8.11)	24.47(8.18)	22.77(7.69)	3.33	.020	.03	1>3>2>4
TR	26.46(6.98)	25.13(7.08)	26.69(6.62)	27.08(5.47)	1.44	.231	.01	4>3>1>2

(*df*₁, *df*₂, *df*₃, *df*₄, *df*₅=299)

Note. Dimensions of Source Credibility Scale(CO=Competence, GO=Goodwill, TR=Trust),AD=Academic dishonesty scale, CIn=Classroom Incivility.

Table shows mean, standard deviation, and F-values for academic dishonesty, classroom incivility, and perceived instructor credibility(competence, goodwill, trust) across achievement level. Achievement level is determined by GPA(Grade point average). 2-2.5GPA indicates low achievers, 2.6-3 range indicates moderately low achievers, 3.1-3.5 indicates moderately high achievers whereas 3.6-4 indicates high achievers. Results indicated a significant mean difference across achievement level on academic dishonesty with $F(3,296)=9.25, p<.001$, and classroom incivility with $F(3,296)=4.62, p<.01$. Findings revealed that students having GPA 2.6-3 exhibit the highest academic dishonesty and classroom incivility and students having GPA 3.6-4 exhibit the lowest academic dishonesty and classroom incivility. Besides this, the value of η was 0.08 for academic dishonesty and .04 for classroom incivility which indicated a small effect size. Moreover, the findings indicated a significant mean difference on the Goodwill sub-scale with $F(3,296)=3.33, p<.05$ and an effect size of .03. Results revealed no significant mean differences on the dimensions of competence and trust.

Table 5: Correlation of study variables (N=300)

Variables	1	2	3	4	5
1 Academic Dishonesty	1	.776**	-.395**	-.207**	-.452**
2 Classroom incivility	-	1	-.454**	-.228**	-.520**
3 Competence	-	-	1	.521**	.571**
4 Goodwill	-	-	-	1	.416**
5 Trustworthiness	-	-	-	-	1

Note. *** $p < .001$, ** $p < .01$, * $p < .05$

Table 7 revealed that academic dishonesty has a significant positive correlation with classroom incivility ($r=.776, p<.01$) and a significant negative correlation with

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competence($r=-.395, p<.01$) and goodwill($r=-.207, p<.01$) and trust subscale($r=-.452, p<.01$). Classroom incivility has a significant negative correlation with competence($r=-.454, p<.01$), goodwill ($r=-.228, p<.01$) and trust($r=-.520, p<.01$) subscales. Besides this, competence has a significant positive correlation with other dimensions of the source credibility scale such as goodwill($r=.521, p<.01$) and trust($r=.571, p<.01$). Moreover, the Goodwill subscale has a significant positive correlation with trust sub-scale($r=.416, p<.01$) of source credibility.

Table 6: Simple Linear Regression showing Perceived Instructor Credibility (Independent variable) as a Predictor of Academic Dishonesty (dependent variable) (N=300)

	<i>B</i>	<i>SEB</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>P</i>
Constant	85.44	4.375		19.529	.000
Competence	-.590	.175	-.27	-3.37	.001
Goodwill	.124	.139	.054	.894	.372
Trustworthiness	-.990	.181	-.35	-5.48	.000

Note. $R = .484$, $R^2 = .234$

Table shows the impact of three subscales of perceived instructor credibility (i.e. competence, goodwill, trustworthiness) on academic dishonesty among university students. The R^2 value of .23 revealed that the predictor variable explained 23% of the variance in the outcome variable with $F(3,296) = 30.15, p > .001$. The findings revealed that competence and trust negatively predict academic dishonesty with ($\beta = -.27, p < .001$) and ($\beta = -.35, p < .001$) respectively. Besides this, goodwill doesn't significantly predict academic dishonesty.

Table 7: Simple Linear Regression showing Perceived Instructor Credibility (Independent variable) as a Predictor of Classroom Incivility (Dependent Variable) (N=300)

	<i>B</i>	<i>SEB</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>P</i>
Constant	49.48	2.274		21.76	.000
Competence	-.380	.091	-.266	-4.18	.000
Goodwill	.097	.072	.077	1.35	.180
Trustworthiness	-.630	.094	-.401	-6.72	.000

Note. $R = .558$, $R^2 = .311$

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Table shows the impact of three dimensions of Perceived Instructor Credibility (i.e. competence, goodwill, trustworthiness) on Classroom incivility among university students. The R^2 value of .31 revealed that the predictor variable explained .31% of the variance in the outcome variable with $F(3,296)=44.63, p<.001$. The findings revealed that competence and trust negatively predict classroom incivility with ($\beta=-.26, p<.001$) and ($\beta=-.40, p<.001$) respectively. Besides this, goodwill doesn't significantly predict classroom incivility.

Figure: Summary of the Correlation Analysis

The figure summarized the results of the research study. It highlights the relationship of all dimensions of perceived instructor credibility (i.e. competence, goodwill, trustworthiness) with academic dishonesty and classroom incivility. It revealed that all dimensions of perceived instructor credibility (competence, goodwill, trustworthiness) has a significant negative relationship with academic dishonesty and classroom incivility. The figure also indicated a positive relationship between the two dependent variables (i.e. academic dishonesty and classroom incivility).

Discussion

This research was conducted to find the correlation between perceived instructor credibility, academic dishonesty and classroom incivility.

According to the first hypothesis of the study, there will be a negative relationship of perceived instructor credibility will classroom incivility and academic dishonesty. As perceived instructor credibility has three dimensions such as competence, goodwill and trustworthiness, a separate correlation of all three dimensions was determined with academic dishonesty and classroom incivility. The results of correlation analysis confirmed the hypothesis as academic dishonesty and classroom incivility has significant negative relationship with all dimensions of perceived instructor credibility. These findings suggest that when students perceive their teachers as more

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competent, caring and trustworthy they are less likely to be involved in academic dishonesty and classroom incivility.

The second hypothesis of the study suggested that Students with higher academic grades will be lower on Classroom incivility and academic dishonesty in comparison to low achievers. The academic grades/academic achievement was determined on the basis of students' grade point average (GPA) in the last semester. The results from ANOVA analysis confirmed the hypothesis by indicating that students with high academic grades score less on academic dishonesty and classroom incivility as compared to low achievers. The results also indicated that students having a GPA of 2.6-3 exhibit the greatest academic dishonesty and classroom incivility and students having a GPA in the range of 3.6-4 exhibit the lowest level of these behaviors.

The third hypothesis of the study suggested that male students/boys are more likely to be involved in academic dishonesty and classroom incivility as compared to female students/girls. The t-test analysis across gender confirmed this hypothesis partially. According to t-test results, there is a significant difference between male and female students in academic dishonesty and male students were more involved in academic dishonesty. On the other hand, according to the results of the present research study there is not any significant difference between male and female students on classroom incivility suggesting that both male and female students have an equal probability to involve in classroom incivility.

The fourth hypothesis of this research study proposed that Academic dishonesty will have a positive correlation to classroom incivility. The findings of the research align with the hypothesis by demonstrating a positive correlation between academic dishonesty with classroom incivility. These findings suggest that students who are involved in classroom incivility are more likely to be involved in academic dishonesty and vice versa.

The linear regression analysis was used to find out whether the independent variable (i.e. perceived instructor credibility) significantly predicts the two dependent variables of the study (i.e. academic dishonesty and classroom incivility). Firstly, regression analysis was performed on all dimensions of IV (i.e. competence, goodwill, trustworthiness) and academic dishonesty. The results of this regression analysis are presented in Table 6 which shows the predictive relationship between competence and trust subscales of perceived instructor credibility that significantly confirms the fifth hypothesis.

Secondly, regression analysis was performed on all dimensions of IV (i.e. competence, goodwill, trustworthiness) and classroom incivility. The results of this regression analysis are presented in Table 7 which shows the predictive relationship between competence and trust subscales of perceived instructor credibility and classroom incivility that significantly confirms the fifth hypothesis.

The findings reveal that competence is a significant negative predictor of academic dishonesty and classroom incivility. This suggests that students who perceive their teachers as having higher levels of competence such as an expert in the subject he is teaching or knowledge he is sharing in the class are less likely to engage in different forms of academic dishonesty and classroom incivility. The findings also reveal that trust is also a significant negative predictor of these disruptive behaviors. This suggests that students who perceive their teachers as trustworthy, faithful, nice, honest, responsible and kind are also less likely to engage in these behaviors. However,

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the results of the regression analysis also indicated that teachers' perception of having high levels of goodwill (i.e. who are student-centered, empathetic and care for their student's interests) does significantly predict academic dishonesty and classroom incivility.

The findings of this study emphasize the significance of perceived instructor/university teachers' credibility in influencing student engagement in disruptive behaviors such as academic dishonesty and classroom incivility. Hence Instructor credibility plays a crucial role in students' better learning and to prevent them from different types of negative behaviors. When teachers are perceived as credible by students, it leads to many positive outcomes for the educational process.

Limitations and Recommendations

The present study has certain limitations that should be acknowledged in future research. Firstly, the study utilized a cross-sectional design. Future research could adopt a longitudinal design to examine the relationship between study variables. Secondly, the study relied on self-reported measures, which commonly involve potential biases such as social desirability and common method variance. To address these biases and improve the validity of the results, future research could employ multi-method approaches by using objective measures and data from various perspectives. Beside this, the study focused on the impact of instructor credibility as perceived by the students. Different types of factors such as students' past grades, students' values etc influence student perception related to teachers. It is recommended to explore the impact of student subjectiveness on their perception of teachers' credibility. Finally, the sample of our research included only university students of BS level. There is a future need to replicate the study with other lower and higher education levels such as school and college level students, MS and Ph.D. students etc.

Implications

The present study has several implications for the whole education system. Firstly, the study highlighted the importance of perceived instructor credibility as predictor of different unhealthy and disruptive behaviors such as academic dishonesty and classroom incivility among students. This suggests that students' perception of their instructor's credibility (i.e. competence and trustworthiness) influences student engagement in different disruptive behaviors. The provision of proper teacher training programs, workshops, and seminars to the teachers to increase their credibility can benefit the education system.

Secondly, the study highlighted the impact of different personal traits of students such as gender, and achievement level(determined by GPA) on their engagement in different

disruptive behaviors. According to the results, male students are more likely to be involved in academic dishonesty. Besides this, low achievers have a greater chance of involvement in these behaviors. By focusing on these vulnerable groups such as male students and low achievers, teachers can overcome the frequency of these disruptive behaviors.

Finally, the study also suggested that students who are involved in one type of disruptive behavior are more likely to be involved in other types as well. So, providing

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proper guidance and counseling at the initial level to the students who were previously involved in some type of disruptive behavior can help to stop these behaviors from intensifying. By controlling these behaviors, educational institutes can generate better citizens as well.

Conclusion

In short, improving instructor's credibility prevents disruptive behaviors (i.e. academic dishonesty and classroom incivility) of students and not only benefits the students, teachers and the education system but the society as a whole.

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